

personnel—quickly recognizing the warnings as bogus—were much more outspoken in their criticisms, as my article points out.

I learned about the Stockton, California, incident when my article was in press; after examining news stories, I concluded that it had no direct connection to the “Lights Out!” warnings. On September 18, 1992, a driver there used a hand signal to alert a driver behind him at a stoplight that his headlights were out. The driver of this second car, taking this as a sign of disrespect, shot at the first car, killing Kelly Freed, 29, a passenger, who was a longtime popular employee of a local school system, although not a teacher. In August 1993, at the sentencing, the prosecutor suggested that the convicted killer had acted “to save face with his fellow gang members”; however, the defense attorney denied that his client belonged to a gang. Never was a gang initiation mentioned in connection with this tragic case, and in February 1995, in articles about efforts to establish a Kelly Freed Teen Center in Stockton, no reference was made to gangs.

The differences in details between this actual crime and the supposed planned attacks described in the warnings, plus the fact that never in any news stories about the warnings—nor in any of the faxed warnings themselves—was the Stockton case mentioned, all suggest that the “Lights Out!” story developed independently.

Critique of Antievolution Paper

In Dan Larhammar’s otherwise excellent article (“Severe Flaws in Scientific Study Criticizing Evolution,” March/April 1995), the author errs by referring to “evidence . . . that argues against evolution as a phenomenon.” As he states earlier in the same paragraph, “evolution is the process that has led to the life forms that inhabit Earth today.” Because *evolution* is the word that scientists use to refer to that process, whose occurrence is beyond question in the context of scientific discourse, there can be no scientific evidence that it did not occur. The evidence the author discusses, like much other evidence, may support or contradict a particular theory of *how* evolution occurs, but only outside the context of science, e.g., in creationist literature, can any scientific evidence be said to argue *whether* evolution occurred. SKEPTICAL INQUIRER’S editors should be most careful to ensure that

such unscientific language never appears in one of its scientific articles.

Stan Kurzban
Chappaqua, N.Y.

Vitamin C and Illness

This exchange continues a debate begun in the May-June Letters column. —EDITOR

Recently Stephen Barrett claimed that vitamin C supplementation at best only slightly affects the symptoms of the common cold (SI, January-February). Barrett referred to the large-scale studies carried out by Anderson et al. but extracted no actual data from their reports. In their first study, Anderson et al. found that vitamin C supplementation (1-4 g/day) decreased the “numbers of days confined to house” per subject by 48 percent in subjects with a low dietary intake of fruit juices (1). Barrett’s claim that at best there is only a slight reduction in symptoms appears grossly misleading considering the published results (1-4). Unlike Barrett, I have written scientific papers analyzing the effect of vitamin C on the common cold (2-5), and my conclusions are quite different from his. Pauling complained that many of his critics had not read either his texts or the original reports, and gave several detailed examples to support his case (6). Apparently many critics have thought that their main task is to educate the general public on the silliness of vitamin C supplementation, but not to inform themselves about the hard science on the topic.

Harri Hemilä, Ph.D.
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sis of Chalmers’ review. *J. Am. Coll. Nutr.*, 1995, 14:116-123.

5. Hemilä, H. Vitamin C, neutrophils and the symptoms of the common cold. *Pediatr. Infect. Dis. J.*, 1992, 11:779.

6. Pauling, L. *How to Live Longer and Feel Better*. New York: Freeman, 1986.

Stephen Barrett replies:

Anderson’s first study found that the average number of confined days was 1.30 for the vitamin group and 1.87 for the placebo group—about half a day per person—which I calculate to be a 30 percent difference ($.57 \div 1.87$). Subsequent studies by Anderson and others have yielded conflicting results: some show a similar decrease in symptoms, others show none. Thus if a difference in house confinement exists, it is half a day or less, which I think has little practical significance. The “complaint” about “many of his critics” that Hemilä attributes to Pauling is on page 226 of reference 6, where Pauling “surmised” that most physicians had read neither his book (Vitamin C and the Common Cold) nor any of the articles describing the controlled studies of vitamin C. The suggestion that no one who disagrees with Pauling has actually read the scientific literature on vitamin C is presumptuous and incorrect.

Re “The Dark Side of Linus Pauling’s Legacy” by Stephen Barrett (January-February, 1995), I will restrict my comments to the quotation from one of Pauling’s books that megadoses of vitamins “can help in controlling heart disease, cancer and other diseases” and to Barrett’s rejoinder: “No responsible medical or nutritional scientists share this view.”

In 1990 a three-day symposium on the relation between cancer and vitamin C was held at the National Institutes of Health. The report of the symposium proceedings said: “Dr. Gladys Block (NIH) summarized the current epidemiological data on the role of ascorbic acid [vitamin C] in cancer prevention. Of 46 epidemiological studies reported, 33 described significant protective effects on cancer mortality or incidence.”

More recently, a study in the journal *Epidemiology* by Enstrom et al. (May 1992) followed 11,348 subjects for an average of ten years. It reported a decrease of 12 percent in mortality from all causes for those who ate enough fruits and vegetables to provide them with at least 50

mg of vitamin C a day, and a decrease of 29 percent for those who used a vitamin C supplement in addition to the fruits and vegetables. For cardiovascular deaths the corresponding percentages were 13 percent and 36 percent for all subjects, 11 percent and 45 percent for males.

Edgar Villchur
Member, Board of Trustees
Linus Pauling Institute
of Science and Medicine
Palo Alto, Calif.

Science and Beauty

As always, Martin Gardner makes an excellent point in his piece "Science and Beauty" (*SI*, March-April). Knowledge of how the universe works certainly can and should deeply increase one's sense of its loveliness and, yes, mysteriousness.

However, perhaps Gardner overlooks an important source of much emotional reaction against the scientific worldview. Increasingly, scientific findings and theories extend the domain of physical causality into humankind itself. The more thoroughly our thoughts, feelings, and actions are shown to be matters of chemistry and structure, the less room is left for traditional free will, not to mention an immortal soul or a God.

It doesn't really do much good to say that these questions are not subject to empirical test and therefore lie beyond the purview of science. At best, this simply sweeps them under the rug. At worst, it is dishonest. The fact is, most of them are integrally involved with material reality. For example, St. Paul pointed out quite some time ago that Christianity stands or falls by whether or not the resurrection of Christ is a historical fact, i.e. a testable proposition. Moral and ethical standards depend largely on what the nature of the human organism is. And so on. Whether or not they articulate this to themselves, most people are quite able to perceive it, and to many it is a bitter pill to swallow.

Poul Anderson
Orinda, Calif.

In asserting a conflict between "the culture of science" and "the culture of liberal arts," all Martin Gardner accomplishes is to reinforce the fortress mentality I perceive in the pages of *SI*.

The liberal arts are not competitors with science, but rather serve us all as observers of and commentators on the human zoo. Both areas are complementary in creating and maintaining the well-functioning human being, and neither stands independent of the society in which it is found.

Jack Miller
Port Clements, B.C.
Canada

Disparaging Emily Dickinson, Wordsworth, Poe, et al. in the name of scientific skepticism? I can't think of a more foolproof way to alienate the romantics among us.

Surely we can allow the poet enchanted by nature to shun the skeptical lens for a few moments of reverie. I'm a nature poet myself, and I shudder to think that some of my lyrical lines could be skewered by the hardened skeptic as antiscientific.

Please, have some room in your scientific universe for the value of nonscientific experiences—unless you really want the world so entirely intellectually oriented that in your most intimate personal moments you hear the "voice of reason" declaring "I'm so chemically receptive to your pheromones" instead of your heart whispering "I love you"!

Gloria J. Leitner
Boulder, Colo.

I am enjoying your emphasis upon "science and reason." Nobody is ever going to be able to knock out pseudoscience. The world would be a much drearier place if there were no nonsensical ideas to laugh about now and then. For one thing, there would be no place for skeptics. They would be out of meaningful employment. The SKEPTICAL INQUIRER would become a mere memory.

Gone, too, would be many creative people. It takes a great amount of intelligence and ingenuity to produce one good unadulterated scam and then to keep the scientific intelligentsia from uncovering its fallacies.

The beauty of science, in itself, is sufficient. One turns off the credulous when one attacks in full force. I am certain that, by asserting the joys of "science and reason" instead of pure skepticism, you will make many more converts and hopefully avoid some of the negatives, such as lawsuits, for example.

I have enthusiastically read your magazine for a long time.

Lorna J. Simmons
Westland, Mich.

"The X-Files"

After reading Eugene Emery's humorless discussion of "The X-Files" (*SI*, March-April), my response is: "Lighten up Gene, it's fiction."

What's next, a serious critique of the techno-babble on Star Trek?

Daniel Cohen
Cape May Court House, N.J.

Eugene Emery replies:

I don't let the facts get in the way of my enjoyment of "The X-Files," and well-informed fans of the show will recognize the program for what it is—good entertainment.

But my experience with people who have not been exposed to the scientific side of paranormal events, combined with comments I've seen on the X-Files corner of the Internet, suggest that there are also fans who believe they're watching stories based on fact. It gives credence to my motivating concern that, if the program isn't trying to use fiction to lend undeserved legitimacy to the paranormal, it is having that effect on some viewers.

*In the wake of my column, and my News and Comment item about the program that got the Coriolis force backwards (*SI*, May-June 1995), X-Files co-executive producer Glen Morgan wrote me a nice note explaining that the Coriolis description was an unintended error and how, "When asked by fans about these moments in the shows, I enjoy popping their balloons and explaining how I just made it up." Morgan said he and his partner approach each episode as a satire or parody of those people so willing to believe any ridiculous conspiracy or phenomenon placed before them that is labeled supernatural."*

The letters column is a forum for views on matters raised in previous issues. Letters should be no more than 250 words. Due to the volume of letters, not all can be published. They should be typed double-spaced. Address: Letters to the Editor, SKEPTICAL INQUIRER, 944 Deer Dr. NE, Albuquerque, NM 87122.

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ON THE COVER:

Illustration by Brad Marshall

language, a distillation of the best features of natural (unplanned Indo-European languages) and it would be a pity if it failed to become what its inventor intended, a second language for all mankind.

Stewart Campbell
Edinburgh, Scotland, U.K.

I found Martin Gardner's article on artificial languages fascinating. Since he is my favorite polymath, it is with trepidation that I venture the following.

It's stated that the "Hebrews tried to scale the heavens by building the Tower of Babel." If one takes the Old Testament account at face value, it was all of humanity that undertook that project not long after Noah's flood, the Hebrews having yet to arrive on the scene. They presumably descended from Eber, who was either Noah's great-great-grandson or great-great-great-grandson.

"Why did Adam name the elephant an *elephant*?" we're asked. "Because, goes an old joke, it *looked* like an elephant." The joke appears in several of Mark Twain's sketches, although in his versions it's always Eve who does the naming. In *Extract from Adam's Diary*, Adam says, "Been examining the great waterfall. It is the finest thing on the estate, I think. The new creature calls it Niagara Falls. . . . Says it *looks* like Niagara Falls. . . . always that same pretext is offered—it *looks* like the thing. There is the dodo, for instance. Says the moment one looks at it one sees at a glance that it 'looks like a dodo.' It looks no more like a dodo than I do."

I was surprised to see no mention of Loglan. Loglan has a dictionary, grammar, and computerized learning assistance. Unfortunately, it has schismatized into at least two rival dialects.

Alfred R. Matthews
Huntsville, Ala.

Your article "Klingon and Other Artificial Languages" incorrectly reported: "*Reader's Digest* publishes an Esperanto edition."

Reader's Digest does not—nor did we ever—publish an Esperanto edition, although we do, however, publish in 18 other languages around the world.

We just thought we should set the record straight for your files.

Craig Lowder
Public Relations Director
Reader's Digest
Pleasantville, N.Y.

Martin Gardner replies:

I have not been able to find where I saw a statement that Reader's Digest had an Esperanto edition. I am grateful to Reader's Digest for correction of the mistake.

Talk Shows Respect the Masses

Since March of this year, almost every major newspaper and magazine has published an article condemning the genre of TV talk. Without exception I have found these articles patronizing, elitist, simplistic, and moralistic. With Gene Emery's "A Psychologist Studies the 'Shameless' Talk Shows and She's Angry," (*SI*, July/August 1995), SKEPTICAL INQUIRER has joined this orgy of self-righteousness.

From the SKEPTICAL INQUIRER I'd expect criticism of the accepted point of view; instead I see endorsement.

Emery's article begins with quotations from Vicki Abt, who wrote an interesting but, in my opinion, simplistic essay about talk shows last year for the *Journal of Popular Culture*. Abt tells us that while watching a videotaped murder on an episode of "Sally Jessy Raphael" she "freaked out. I was screaming. I was crying." She asks, "What is the point of this?"

A good question, but one she doesn't answer. Instead she jumps to the same conclusions other critics have: Talk shows are freak shows, the guests are "white trash" or "pure dreck," the audience is a collection of heartless voyeurs, the hosts are greedy, lying, and manipulative.

It's easier to discuss others than to analyze ourselves. Had Abt done a little self-analysis she would have discovered one important reason people watch talk shows: emotional involvement. She was crying and screaming, yet it didn't occur to her that she was supposed to.

Professor Richard Lazarus explains in the book *Passion and Reason: Making Sense of our Emotions* (Oxford University

Press, 1994): "If members of the audience are not moved, they would leave, or become bored and inattentive. . . . Only when the plot fails to touch the audience is emotion absent. This means that to be popular with audiences a play must portray real-life themes that are personally meaningful to the audience and must generate emotions. . . ." This is true of all successful works of art, from Homer to the present. From Homer to Oprah.

Abt and her fellow critics feel a certain bonding to Plato, who opposed poets and the mass audience. He believed both were irrational and amoral. Abt sees danger in talk shows for the same reason Plato saw danger in theater: they indulge in the emotions of pity and fear. Plato and Abt prefer repression to indulgence.

When Sally Jessy Raphael said on America Online "I believe that it is more important to do the shows that the majority of the public asks for than to determine by myself what I want them to see" she was demonstrating a greater respect for the masses than any of her critics can comprehend.

Damion Doohan
Windsor, Calif.

More on Vitamin C and Illness

Harri Hemilä, in a letter (*SI*, July/August 1995) responding to Stephen Barrett's "The Dark Side of Linus Pauling's Legacy" (January/February 1995) cites Anderson et al. (1) on the effect of vitamin C supplements. He says the Anderson study "found that vitamin C supplementation (1-4 g/day) decreased the 'numbers of days confined to house' per subject by 48 percent in subjects with a low dietary intake of fruit juices."

Barrett's reply in the same issue to the letter challenges Hemilä's reporting accuracy, but Hemilä is correct: Anderson et al. reported (Table IV) that for subjects taking three ounces of juice or fewer a day, the average confinement caused by colds or other illness was 1.87 days for the placebo group and 0.98 days for the vitamin group; $(1.87 - 0.98)/1.87 = 47.59$ percent.

Barrett calculates the reduction in disability time as 30 percent. A reading of

Anderson et al. shows that this percentage is derived from their Table II, in which they report results for *all* of their subjects, including those taking four or more ounces of juice.

Both percentages are meaningful; the larger of the two indicates that vitamin C supplements are especially useful for persons who have diet deficiencies. Barrett, however, doesn't say he is citing a different part of the Anderson data, and thus makes it seem that Hemilä has either misread or misrepresented Anderson.

Edgar Villchur
Linus Pauling Institute of
Science and Medicine
Palo Alto, Calif.

I. Anderson, T. W., D. B. Reid, and G. H. Beaton. Vitamin C and the common cold: A double-blind trial. *Can. Med. Assoc. J.* 1972, 107:503-8.

Stephen Barrett, M.D., replies:

Villchur is correct that Hemilä and I referred to different figures. The idea that people with a dietary deficiency might benefit from increasing their intake of the missing nutrient(s) is hardly novel. In most cases, this should be done by improving one's diet rather than by taking supplements. There is no evidence that ingesting amounts of vitamin C beyond what the body needs will prevent colds. Taking supplements (or drinking extra fruit juice) may slightly reduce the symptoms of a cold, but adequately nourished people have little or nothing to gain by doing this.

I comment further on the vitamin C matter—three letters (May/June issue) and specifically the letter (July/August) from Edgar Villchur of the Linus Pauling Institute. He recounts Gladys Block's summary of epidemiologic data on vitamin C, stating that 33 of 46 papers show "significant protective effects on cancer mortality and incidence."

I reviewed the references in her paper and found that all referred to vitamin C in the *diet*. None referred to ascorbate supplementation. The same conference had a paper by Stadtman about the chemical dangers of ascorbate, which in high dose causes denaturation of proteins, nucleic acids, and lipids. Ascorbate destroys mammalian red

blood cells, and has caused death from red cell destruction in humans. It is a pro-oxidant, acting by reducing iron and copper which then produce oxygen free radicals. Ascorbate is listed as a toxin in biochemistry texts because of this activity.

The Enstrom epidemiologic paper that showed increasing cancer protection with increasing ascorbate supplementation did not consider the likely decreased fat intake in people who would supplement their diets with ascorbate. The Enstrom paper demonstrates the dangers of over-interpretation of epidemiologic data, and confused association with cause.

Dr. Barrett was correct in stating that ascorbate probably has no effect on viral illness. The tighter the controls in the Anderson Toronto studies, the less the ascorbate effect. The five best done, prospective studies showed no effect (references on request). The book is nearly closed on the subject of vitamin C supplementation for prevention and treatment of colds, "flus," and cancer. Might as well reopen the great Laetrile debate.

Wallace Sampson, M.D.
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Nature of Scientific Investigation

In a letter in the July/August issue, a reader chastised Dan Larhammar for "unscientific language" for referring to "evidence . . . that argues against evolution as a phenomenon." The reader's point was that, since evolution is true, it is impossible for there to be evidence against it.

Unfortunately, this position shows a profound ignorance of the nature of scientific investigation. In virtually every scientific topic of importance, there is a wide spectrum of evidence both for and against (and often some pointing in yet other directions). This is all evidence, whether true or not, and this is what must be weighed. There is no a priori (nor easy) way to separate credible from false evidence—instead, evidence must be tested bit by bit. To use "what all scientists accept" or "the known truth" as

criteria for credibility would put the scientist exactly in the same league as the creation "scientist" who, since he or she already knows evolution is false, can find no evidence for evolution.

Consider as an example that 50 years ago, accepted scientific theory held that the continents were immovable. Evidence to the contrary was held to be patently false by most scientists. We now accept plate tectonics as proved beyond reasonable doubt. Unwillingness to consider evidence because it does not fit our conception of "truth" is a sure way to stagnation and error.

Arthur H. Harris
Laboratory for Environmental
Biology, Centennial Museum
University of Texas at El Paso
El Paso, Texas

Neanderthal Brains

Robert Baker, attempting to refute Terence Hines's claim that Baker's book *Hidden Memories* is full of factual errors (*SI*, July/August 1995), states that "truly 'modern' man did not appear until the Cro-Magnon brain showed a tremendous increase over that of the Neanderthal." This is blatantly incorrect: Neanderthals had brains at least as large as early *Homo sapiens* ("Cro-Magnon"), and definitely larger than modern humans. The endocranial volume of Neanderthals ranged from 1245 ml to 1740 ml, with an average of 1485 ml ($n = 20$, $SD = 142.4$), which is comparable to the mean of "Cro-Magnon" (Holloway 1985). The mean endocranial capacity of modern humans ranges from 1200 ml to 1500 ml, depending on the population. The large brain size of Neanderthals is a well-known fact; while I have given the primary reference above, this data is mentioned in both textbooks (Klein 1989) and popular works (Stringer and Gamble 1993).

David DeGusta
Laboratory for Human
Evolutionary Studies
University of California
Berkeley, Calif.

References

Holloway, R. L. 1985. "The Poor Brain of *Homo Sapiens Neanderthalensis*: See What You

20 The GAO Roswell Report and Congressman Schiff

PHILIP J. KLASS

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JOHN H. TAYLOR, RAYMOND A. EVE, AND FRANCIS B. HARROLD

The various pseudoscientific beliefs cannot be explained as if they were a single phenomenon. At least two major categories—creationism and fantastic science—exist, and they are causally distinct.

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RICHARD WISEMAN, MATTHEW SMITH, AND JEFF WISEMAN

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MICHAEL MUSSACHIA

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ROBERT E. BARTHOLOMEW

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